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FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF OILENTRAPPED FLOATING ALGINATE BEADS OF RANITIDINE HYDROCHLORIDE FOR SUSTAINED RELEASE

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation deals with the preparation and evaluation of oilentrapped floating alginate beads of Ranitidine hydrochloride for sustained release. The beads were prepared by ionotropic emulsion-gelation method. The prepared beads were evaluated for percentage yield, entrapment efficiency, micromeretic studies, *in-vitro* drug release studies, stability studies. Ranitidine hydrochloride floating beads which are prepared with polymers such as polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP) and hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC), were free flowing and showed almost spherical shape. The beads showed excellent floating properties throughout the study period. Polymer such as polyvinyl pyrrolidone effectively sustained the drug release from the bead formulations. It can be concluded that the polymer plays a major role in the design of formulation F12. Gastro retentive floating formulation containing Ranitidine hydrochloride (F12 Formulation) gave slow and maximum drug release over 12 h. The dissolution data was also plotted in accordance with korsmeyer-peppas model (where n is the release exponent). Applicability of data indicating Non-Fickian diffusion as mechanism of drug release. The drug release followed first order kinetics. Hence it was considered as the best formulation.

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INTRODUCTION

Oral drug delivery system is the most widely utilized route of administration among all the routes that have been explored for delivery of drugs via pharmaceutical products of different dosage forms. Oral route is considered as the most natural, uncomplicated, convenient and safe due to its ease of administration, patient acceptance, and cost-effective manufacturing process. Controlled drug delivery systems have been developed which are capable of controlling the of drug delivery, sustaining the duration of therapeutic activity and/or targeting the delivery of drug to a tissue. Ranitidine hydrochloride is a H₂-receptor antagonist. Ranitidine is absorbed only in the initial part of the small intestine and the low bioavailability (50%) and short biological half-life (2.5-3 h) so that the Ranitidine following oral administration favors development of sustained release formulation [1].

The floating system, mainly because the floating system does not adversely affect the motility of the GI tract. Calcium alginate (Ca-Alg) is the result of the complexation of the polygluronic sequences by calcium ion known to be insoluble and resistant to acidic media. The alginate floating dosage form are obvious, cheap and abundant sources, excellent biocompatibility, and total degradation without hazardous by-products. The calcium alginate (Ca-Alg) gel beads by freeze drying. The beads were approximately 2.5 mm in diameter and floated on agitated acidic media (0.1N HCl+0.05% Tween 80) for over 12 h. The floating beads were radiolabelled with pertechnetate (^{99m}Tc) and *in-vivo* test revealed gastric retention of these beads ranged from 5.5 to 9 h. Amoxicillin release from these alginate beads was conducted most samples, however, there was little sustained release of the drug: the majority of drug was released in a burst during 60 min. Higher drug loadings could be achieved at the expense of faster release and lower buoyancy. The floating alginate beads incorporating amoxicillin recently. The beads were produced by dropwise addition of alginate into calcium chloride solution, followed by removal of gel beads and freeze drying. The beads containing the dissolved drug remained buoyant for 20 h and high drug loading levels were achieved [2-7].

The erodible multi-unit floating Gastro retentive controlled drug delivery system with an intention of achieving a controlled release profile that is consistent with prolonged retention time. Gel beads made solely of calcium alginate was found to lack sufficient and consistent buoyancy over long hours of administration. In contrast, the oil incorporated alginate gel beads floated constantly under the condition of body temperature and continuous agitation for more than 24 h. Drug release profiles were influenced by the relative hydrophilicities of drugs. A slow first order ibuprofen release was achieved with drug encapsulation in oil. Sustained release for more than 12 h was also achieved for hydrophilic (drugs such as niacinamide and metoclopramide HCl, with the rate-control being achieved by means of an acid resistant Eudragit coating. Such an alginate based GRDS is hence thought to be able to sustain the release of both hydrophobic and hydrophilic drugs over 12 h, while remaining afloat in the gastric fluid [8-21].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials.

S.No.	Chemical Name	Supplier
1	Ranitidine hydrochloride	Yarrow chem. products, Mumbai
2	Sodium alginate	Qualikems fine chemical Pvt.Ltd
3	Peanut oil	Best life organic ltd.
4	Polyvinyl pyrrolidone (PVP)	Oxford laboratory reagent
5	Hydroxyethyl cellulose	Yarrow chem. Products, Mumbai

Methodology

Standard curve of Ranitidine hydrochloride in 0.1N Hcl solution:

Preparation of 0.1N Hcl

0.85ml of concentrated Hcl was pipetted out and added into 100ml volumetric flask containing 99.15 ml of water. This gives 100ml of 0.1N Hcl as per I.P.

Preparation of dilutes for Standard curve

Step1: First 25mg of drug was taken and added to 25 ml of 0.1N Hcl (The solution is 1000µg/ml)

Step2: From the above solution 0.4, 0.8, 1.2, 1.6 and 2 ml were taken and added up to 10ml of 0.1N Hcl to each volumetric flask (so that 40µg/ml, 80µg/ml, 120µg/ml, 160µg/ml and 200µg/ml were prepared respectively). The absorbances were measured at 313.5nm wavelength in UV spectrophotometer.

Drug Excipients Compatibilities:

The pure drug and along with its formulation excipients were subjected to compatibility studies and carried out by mixing definite proportions of drug, excipients and kept in glass vials which were stored at 40°C and 75±5% RH for one month. Physical observation of samples was done for every week for any color change or lump formation.

Preparation of Ranitidine hydrochloride loaded alginate beads by using Ionotropic emulsion-gelation method:

Blank beads with 8 % (v/v), 10 % (v/v) and 12 % (v/v) of peanut oil were prepared as part of initial trials. Out of which 12 % (V/V) beads were only floated; hence 12 % (v/v) beads were prepared with drug. In this method, sodium alginate and different polymer ratios of polyvinyl pyrrolidone and hydroxyethyl cellulose were dissolved in 10 ml distilled water to get clear polymeric dispersions. Ranitidine was dissolved in 5 ml distilled water and this solution was added to polymeric solution and mixed homogeneously in a 50ml beaker. To the above mixture peanut oil 12 % (v/v) was added and stirred to ensure emulsion stabilization. It was mixed at 600rpm using a magnetic stirrer for 10min. The bubble free drug-loaded emulsion was extruded through a 24-G syringe needle into 50ml of calcium chloride (5% w/v) solution maintained under gentle agitation. The beads were allowed to remain in the same solution for 30 min to improve their mechanical strength at room temperature. The formed beads were separated, washed with water and allowed to dry at room temperature overnight.

Table No 1: Formulation of floating alginate beads.

Ingredients	Formulation Code											
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
Ranitidine hydrochloride(g)	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Peanut oil(ml)	4	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Sodium alginate(g)	1.5	1.5	1	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75	0.75
HEC(g)	-	-	-	-	0.25	0.5	0.75	-	-	-	-	-
PVP (g)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.25	0.5	0.75	1	1.5

Evaluation of alginate beads [8-12]:

Visual analysis: The formed beads of different formulations were inspected.

Percentage yield: The percentage yield for the different formulations was calculated by the formula.

$$\text{Percentage yield} = \frac{\text{Total weight of beads recovered}}{\text{total weight (drug + polymer+oil)}} \times 100$$

Beads water uptake

Beads water uptake in this case was presented as normalized weight gain ratio as defined below: $Y = m_w/m_d$

Where, Y is the normalized weight gain ratio,

m_w , the bead weight after swelling (including water uptake),

m_d is the initial dry bead weight.

10 dry beads were taken from individual formulation and weighed (initial weight). Then these were added into 50ml of 0.1N HCL taken individually as per formulation and allowed them to remain for 12hrs for water uptake i.e. (0.1N HCL). Then swollen beads were collected accordingly and weighed (bead weight after swelling). Beads water uptake of the different floating formulations was calculated.

Drug Entrapment Efficiency

An accurately weighed drug loaded beads (100 mg) were crushed in a mortar and added to 100ml of 0.1N HCL. This mixture was kept overnight under stirring to elute complete drug from the polymer matrix. The mixture was filtered through whatmann filter paper and analyzed spectrophotometrically at a wavelength of 313.5nm. Using a regression equation derived from the standard graph ($r^2 = 0.996$). The drug entrapment efficiency was calculated by the equation, as per I.P.

$$\text{DEE} = \left(\frac{\text{actual drug content}}{\text{theoretical drug content}} \right) \times 100.$$

Micromeretic studies:

The beads were characterized for their micromeretic properties such as bulk density, tapped density, hausner's ratio, carr's index and angle of repose. All the analysis were carried out in triplicate. The particle size was determined using optical microscope.

Particle Size Measurement

To determine the particle size of alginate beads, dry beads from each formulation were measured using an optical microscope at a magnification of 50x with an ocular micrometer which was calibrated using a stage micrometer

Floating Lag Time

The time between the introduction of beads into the medium and its buoyancy to the upper one third of the beaker is known as (floating lag time). The beads were introduced into 100ml of 0.1N Hcl solution and observed for floating lag time.

Duration of Buoyancy

The time for which the formulation constantly floated on the surface of the medium (floating duration) was measured simultaneously as a part of dissolution studies as per USP.

In-vitro Drug Release Studies:

In-vitro drug release studies of Ranitidine hydrochloride were studied using dissolution apparatus USP type I basket method with a stirring speed of 100 rpm at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ in 900 ml of 0.1N HCl for 12 h. Accurately weighed quantity of beads equivalent to 100 mg of drug of each formulation were added into vessels and set for rpm. The 5 ml samples were taken at preselected time intervals with replacement of equal volume of dissolution media. The collected samples were diluted and the absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically at 313.5 nm. The percentage of ranitidine released at various time intervals were calculated.

Table No 2: Dissolution protocol.

Dissolution apparatus	USP Type I
Dissolution medium	900 ml 0.1N HCl
Temperature	$37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$
RPM	100
Wavelength	313.5nm

Assay:

100 mg equivalent beads were taken and dissolved in 100 ml 0.1N HCl and further dilutions were carried out to get 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ then the resultant solution was observed for absorbance at 313.5 nm using U.V. Spectrophotometer.

Infrared Spectroscopic Studies:

Identification of the pure drug and polymer were performed using infrared spectroscopy. Infrared spectroscopy by KBr pellet method was carried out on drug and polymer. They are compressed under 10 ton pressure in a hydraulic press to form a transparent pellet. The pellet was scanned in a spectrophotometer and peaks obtained were identified.

Stability Studies:

Stability testing of drug products begins as a part of drug discovery and ends with the demise of the compound or commercial product. To assess drug and formulation stability, short-term stability studies were done for 1 month. The stability studies were carried out on the most satisfactory formulations. The optimized formulation beads were taken in storage vial and kept at normal room temperature condition ($40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}/75 \pm 5\% \text{RH}$) for one month. The beads were withdrawn and evaluated for physical properties, and *in-vitro* drug release. . Samples were withdrawn at the end of 30 th day and physical characters like color change if any were recorded. Then beads were withdrawn and evaluated for physical properties, and *in-vitro* drug release.

RESULTS

Drug-exceptient compatibility studies:

S No	Drug and excipient	Observation	
		Storage condition / duratio Initia	37°C/75±5%RH 1M
1	Ranitidine hydrochloride	Pale yellowish crystalline powder	No Characteristic Change
2	Ranitidine Hcl+polyvinylpyrrolidine	Pale yellowish crystalline powder	No Characteristic Change
3	Ranitidine Hcl+hydroxyl ethyl cellulose	Pale yellowish crystalline powder	No Characteristic Change

Standard Graph of Ranitidine in 0.1N Hcl:

Standard graph of Ranitidine hydrochloride was constructed between Concentration of drug and absorbance. The standard graph of Ranitidine Hcl was in graph no1 with regression equation $y = 0.004x - 0.008$ and coefficient of determination (R^2) was found to be 0.996.

Figure 1: Standard Graph of Ranitidine hydrochloride in 0.1N HCL.

Percentage yield:

Table No.3: Percentage yield of different formulations.

S. No.	Formulation Code	Percentage yield
1	F1	81.00%±0.12
2	F2	95.40%±0.23
3	F3	90.00%±0.25
4	F4	97.4%±0.14
5	F5	96.01%±0.10
6	F6	95.60%±0.16
7	F7	97.30%±0.20
8	F8	94.12%±0.35
9	F9	96.3%±0.21
10	F10	92.04%±0.19
11	F11	83.35%±0.13
12	F12	98.13%±0.25

Swelling properties:

Table No. 4: Swelling properties of different formulations.

Formulation code	Dry weight (g)	Weight after swelling (g)	Weight gain ratio
F1	0.60±0.15	0.876±0.20	1.46±0.25
F2	0.43±0.25	0.877±0.13	2.03±0.14
F3	0.42±0.19	0.647±0.28	1.54±0.20
F4	0.34±0.12	0.480±0.23	1.41±0.26
F5	0.33±0.10	0.420±0.15	1.27±0.29
F6	0.35±0.25	0.480±0.19	1.37±0.15
F7	0.34±0.19	0.699±0.35	2.05±0.14
F8	0.36±0.25	0.514±0.19	1.42±0.18
F9	0.31±0.14	0.411±0.28	1.32±0.10
F10	0.40±0.26	0.730±0.16	1.82±0.12
F11	0.46±0.31	0.760±0.25	1.65±0.39
F12	0.36±0.11	0.490±0.17	1.36±0.14

Drug entrapment efficiency.

Table No 5: Drug entrapment efficiency of different formulations.

S.No	Formulation code	Percentage entrapment
1	F1	73.33%±0.20
2	F2	90.01%±0.15
3	F3	86.66%±0.23
4	F4	95.03%±0.22
5	F5	93.33%±0.19
6	F6	90.06%±0.10
7	F7	95.13%±0.12
8	F8	90.12%±0.26
9	F9	93.33%±0.30
10	F10	90.20%±0.19
11	F11	73.33%±0.30
12	F12	96.66%±0.29

Micromeretic properties

Table No 6: Micromeretic properties of different formulations.

Formulation code	Angle of repose (θ)	Bulk density (g/ml)	Tapped density (g/ml)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's ratio	Mean particle size (µm)
F1	18.38±0.23	0.55±0.31	0.59±0.20	6.77±0.15	1.07±0.19	1912.50±0.23
F2	21.27±0.14	0.55±0.21	0.59±0.13	6.77±0.19	1.07±0.12	1593.75±0.15
F3	22.39±0.35	0.41±0.35	0.43±0.10	4.65±0.12	1.04±0.10	2018.75±0.23
F4	16.93±0.15	0.53±0.10	0.54±0.36	2.57±0.23	1.02±0.23	1593.75±0.19
F5	18.41±0.21	0.57±0.15	0.61±0.25	6.62±0.10	1.07±0.35	2125.00±0.10
F6	14.08±0.20	0.58±0.24	0.60±0.19	2.32±0.19	1.02±0.22	2018.75±0.30
F7	19.74±0.19	0.53±0.36	0.55±0.11	4.12±0.25	1.04±0.18	2231.25±0.24
F8	18.51±0.14	0.54±0.14	0.55±0.25	2.35±0.31	1.02±0.15	2125.00±0.14
F9	17.99±0.10	0.66±0.19	0.70±0.13	5.71±0.17	1.06±0.21	1806.25±0.18
F10	20.91±0.35	0.55±0.23	0.57±0.25	3.50±0.13	1.03±0.14	1806.25±0.13
F11	15.61±0.21	0.58±0.36	0.54±0.15	1.69±0.15	1.01±0.10	2231.25±0.19
F12	18.01±0.25	0.580±0.28	0.62±0.31	6.45±0.22	1.06±0.20	2125.00±0.25

Figure 2: Floating of Ranitidine hydrochloride beads in 0.1N Hcl.

Floating properties:

Table No 7: Floating properties of different formulations.

Formulation code	Floating lag time (sec)	Duration of buoyancy (h)
F1	120	>12
F2	120	>12
F3	60	>12
F4	30	>12
F5	30	>12
F6	60	>12
F7	60	>12
F8	120	>12
F9	90	>12
F10	60	>12
F11	30	>12
F12	30	>12

In Vitro drug release:

Table No 8: In Vitro drug release for formulations F1 to F12.

Cumulative % drug release						
Formulation code	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Time (hrs)						
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	15.6±0.15	13.6±0.12	17.1±0.18	18±0.28	15.2±0.26	13.8±0.23
1	23.4±0.26	20.2±0.23	21.6±0.26	26.2±0.39	27.1±0.12	17.2±0.15
2	26.1±0.11	25.4±0.28	±26.3±0.22	35.1±0.10	37.2±0.36	20.5±0.20
4	32.5±0.28	30.9±0.27	38.4±0.20	42.8±0.28	47.3±0.25	31.2±0.23
6	43.1±0.15	41.2±0.31	45.8±0.17	53.4±0.18	55.2±0.17	42.9±0.39
8	58.1±0.22	56.9±0.45	58.1±0.25	68.1±0.27	69.2±0.26	50.1±0.19
10	69.8±0.26	65.4±0.25	69.5±0.29	72.4±0.25	74.1±0.25	53.1±0.27
12	70.1±0.20	69.8±0.31	73.2±0.26	75.8±0.36	76.2±0.31	60.9±0.44

Cumulative % drug release						
Formulation code	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
Time (hrs)						
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	12.6±0.11	19.2±0.12	21.6±0.28	23.1±0.31	25.6±0.34	27.3±0.28
1	15.2±0.14	27.3±0.24	29.5±0.39	31.2±0.17	33.2±0.31	35.5±0.39
2	19.8±0.22	38.2±0.20	39.1±0.10	40.9±0.14	42.1±0.18	45.3±0.10
4	28.2±0.14	44.6±0.18	45.2±0.28	47.2±0.27	49.3±0.23	52.9±0.42
6	35.2±0.39	55.9±0.25	58.6±0.20	59.3±0.29	61.8±0.16	69.3±0.13
8	41.6±0.22	69.3±0.28	70.1±0.44	72.4±0.14	73.1±0.25	78.5±0.28
10	47.9±0.27	73.8±0.19	75.2±0.27	78.6±0.22	81.5±0.19	89.1±0.18
12	54.5±0.20	76.9±0.39	78.3±0.25	85.9±0.27	89.7±0.29	98.5±0.27

In vitro drug release kinetic dataTable No. 9: *In vitro* drug release kinetic data of all formulations.

Formulation	Coefficient of determination			
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Korsemyerpeppas
F1	0.945	0.961	0.967	0.952
F2	0.959	0.977	0.973	0.968
F3	0.953	0.985	0.986	0.976
F4	0.912	0.984	0.990	0.976
F5	0.895	0.979	0.989	0.979
F6	0.946	0.992	0.990	0.976
F7	0.953	0.998	0.992	0.983
F8	0.898	0.984	0.989	0.990
F9	0.891	0.988	0.987	0.980
F10	0.908	0.983	0.983	0.986
F11	0.907	0.966	0.987	0.984
F12	0.912	0.840	0.988	0.984

Table No 10: Various dissolution parameters for all formulations.

Formulation	Zero order K_0	First order K_1	'n' value
F1	7.50	0.044	0.814
F2	7.85	0.037	0.618
F3	6.15	0.089	0.793
F4	7.35	0.063	0.268
F5	7.00	0.187	0.298
F6	1.50	0.066	0.268
F7	3.15	0.051	0.628
F8	2.25	0.180	0.288
F9	5.75	0.163	0.319
F10	3.10	0.194	0.371
F11	4.20	0.186	0.494
F12	5.30	0.339	0.567

Figure 3: IR Spectrum of Ranitidine hydrochloride.

Figure 4: IR Spectrum of polymer PVP.

Figure 5: IR Spectrum of polymer HEC.

Figure 6: IR Spectrum of formulation F5.

Stability Studies:

Figure 7: IR Spectrum of formulation F12.

Table No 11: Dissolution profile of F12 formulation kept for stability.

Time(hrs)	% drug release	
	Initial	Final
0	0	0
0.5	27.3±0.28	26.1±0.13
1	35.5±0.39	35.2±0.29
2	45.3±0.10	44.2±0.36
4	52.9±0.42	51.5±0.25
6	69.3±0.13	68.2±0.15
8	78.5±0.28	77.3±0.10
10	89.1±0.18	88.5±0.24
12	98.5±0.27	97.2±0.11

Figure No. 8: Release profile of F12 formulation.

Table No 12: Kinetics of drug release for optimized formulation:

Formulation	zero order (R ²)	first order (R ²)	higuchi (R ²)	korsmeyer and peppas model (R ²)	n	Drug release mechanism
F12	0.912	0.840	0.988	0.9840	0.567	Non- Fickian

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The objective of the present study was to develop floating alginate beads of Ranitidine hydrochloride with a view to increase the dissolution rate. Ranitidine is absorbed in the initial part of the small intestine. This drug is stable in acidic medium. Its elimination half life is nearly about 2-3 h and its bioavailability is 50%. If the dosage form can retain in the stomach as long as possible, to allow for maximum absorption, then the bioavailability could be improved. Gastric floating drug delivery system is one approach where the gastro intestinal residence time is prolonged because of the floating behavior. For this purpose sodium alginate as matrix bead forming agent, peanut oil as buoyancy imparting agent, hydrophilic swellable polymers like polyvinyl pyrrolidone and hydroxyl ethyl cellulose were used as key ingredients. The discussions of various evaluation results were as follows.

The organoleptic characteristics of Ranitidine were found to be a white to pale yellowish crystalline powder. Its melting point was 69-70 °C. As there was no characteristic change of drug with excipients (PVP & HEC) for about one month on storage, these combinations were used for further work.

Studies on Ranitidine hydrochloride beads:

The formulation (F12) sustained highest percentage yield i.e. 98.13% which was F12>F4>F7>F5>F9>F2=F6=F8=F10>F3>F1 observed in this category. The yield values for other formulations in decreasing order was F12>F4>F7>F9>F5>F6>F2>F8>F10>F3>F11>F1. The swelling property of F7 was found to be more because these beads were formulated with sodium alginate and HEC (1.5%) which binds easily with more water molecules and becomes more swellable, thus it showed more swelling property. Out of all the 12 formulations as per F12 formulation showed highest percentage yield of drug i.e. 96.66%; this might be due to increase in polymer molecules binding to drug molecules. All the values of angle of repose were found to be within the prescribed limits which showed excellent flow property. The mean particle size of F7 and F11 formulations were found to be more i.e., (F7&F11=2231.25µm).

From the study of floating properties, it was observed that the floating lag time ranges from 30 sec to 120 sec, whereas the duration of buoyancy was more than 12 h for all formulations F1 to F12. Thus incorporation of peanut oil in beads provides densities that were lower than the density of the release medium. 12% v/v peanut oil was sufficient to achieve proper *in-vitro* floating behavior.

As per the results, *in vitro* dissolution studies for F12 formulation drug release rate was found to be optimum with 98.5±0.27 % released within 12 hrs compared to other formulations F1 to F11. In the first four formulations i.e. F1 to F4, as the concentration of sodium alginate decreased and peanut oil concentration was kept at 12%, the release rate was found to be increased. The release rate of F4 formulation was found to be 75.8±0.36 and among the formulations containing HEC (F5, F6, and F7) at various proportions, formulation F5 showed maximum drug release of 76.2±0.31 within 12 h. Among the formulations containing PVP (F8, F9, F10, F11, and F12) at various proportions, F12 formulation showed maximum drug release of 98.5±0.27 within 12 h.

Pure drug ranitidine hydrochloride exhibited various peaks due to presence of specific functional groups. It was found that, in IR spectra of formulation; all characteristic peaks of pure drug were found intact. This indicates that the drug was compatible with the formulation components. The stability studies were carried under room temperature for 1 month, for the optimized formulation. Then the samples were examined for physical parameters, assay and dissolution profiles (as per USP specifications). The results showed that the formulation was found to be stable.

Release mechanism

Based on the “n” value (0.567) obtained for F12, the drug release was found to follow non-fickian diffusion. This indicates a coupling of the diffusion and erosion mechanisms and it was found that the drug release was controlled by more than one process. The “r²” value for Higuchi was found to be 0.988 indicating that drug release included diffusion as one of the release mechanisms. The drug release kinetics was best explained by first order equation, as plots showed the highest linearity (r² = 0.998). As the drug release was best fitted in first order kinetics, it indicated that the rate of drug release is concentration dependent. Hence for formulation F12 drug release kinetics followed zero order.

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